

Corporate Governance in Turbulent Times: Assessing Firm Performance and Risk in Pakistan During Economic Stability and Crises

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of corporate governance (CG) systems on risk and company performance in Pakistan under stable and crisis conditions. Using eleven years of panel data (2009–2019) from 71 non-financial firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) 100 Index, the study applies random effect models and the penalized least squares regression model. The Corporate Governance Index (CGI), based on key CG factors including blockholder's ownership, independent directors, managerial ownership, CEO duality, institutional ownership, and board ownership serves as a self-assessment measure. Findings indicate no significant relationship between CG and shareholder returns (Tobin's Q, EPS), except for a positive correlation between CG indicators, board ownership earnings, and firm age. While CG exhibits an inverse relationship with shareholder returns, its contribution to overall performance is limited. Additionally, CG and control variables show an insignificant link to risk, whereas Risk1 (a preceding risk factor) is significantly associated with the dependent variable, risk. The study underscores the importance of strong CG practices in enhancing investor confidence and regulatory trust, reinforcing the need for transparent governance frameworks in Pakistan's corporate sector.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Risk, EPS, Firm Performance.*

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Introduction

In today's globalized and competitive economy, the success of a nation's economic system relies heavily on the effectiveness of firms and the structure of corporate governance within its jurisdiction. Firms serve as key entities that drive economic growth and generate value, playing a crucial role in shaping a country's economic stability and progress (ICAN, 2009). Previous research has primarily focused on corporate governance, firm valuation, or performance outcomes (Brown & Caylor, 2006).

Furthermore, the relationship between corporate governance and risk management has also been discussed (Kim & Lu, 2011). A more recent empirical finding highlights the pricing of risk in the fragmented segment of firm risks. Market risks are factored into the pricing within the fragmented segment of stock market returns (Black, Carvalho, Kim, & Black, 2018). In a study, researchers discuss that this may be interpreted as the sensitivity of a firm's market risk to incoming shocks at different frequencies. Most corporate governance studies focus on industrialized economies. Although significant advancements have been made in research on emerging economies in recent years, the literature remains relatively limited. Some studies explore the central question of whether corporate governance influences organizational risk and performance (Brown & Caylor, 2006; Younas et al., 2021). Lau, Lu, & Liang (2016) have shown that the presence of external directors in an organization has a significant impact on organizational risk. Firms with greater independent oversight and higher institutional ownership experienced lower share prices during a crisis. Correspondingly, Black et al., (2018) and Salem et al., (2019) debates, the recent global financial crisis can be attributed to failures and weaknesses in corporate governance arrangements within financial organizations.

There is limited research in the Pakistani context that comprehensively examines firm performance alongside firm risk during both crisis and non-crisis periods. This study will contribute to the literature by focusing on the non-financial sector of Pakistani firms. A broad

set of corporate governance features will be utilized, with a particular focus on the board of directors and CEO duality (CEOD) to establish a comprehensive "governance index" as a measure of governance efficiency. This research will further analyze how these governance factors relate to organizational risk.

The primary objective of this research is to examine the relationship between corporate governance, company performance, and risk in Pakistani non-financial enterprises. This study utilizes a unique dataset that will be novel and unfamiliar to many international readers. A key contribution of this research is the inclusion of a broad range of corporate governance factors in the analysis, incorporating six two-dimensional variables into the model like., Block holders' ownership, CEO duality, board ownership, managerial ownership, institutional investors and independent directors on the board (Ciftci et al., 2019).

Corporate Governance

Corporate governance refers to the system of rules, practices, and processes through which a company is directed and controlled. It involves balancing the interests of various stakeholders, including shareholders, management, customers, suppliers, financiers, government, and the broader community. Corporate governance establishes a framework for achieving a company's objectives, encompassing key areas such as strategic planning, internal controls, performance measurement, and corporate disclosure.

Firm Risk

Firm risk refers to the uncertainty or fluctuations in a company's financial performance, which may impact its ability to fulfill financial obligations and achieve strategic goals. It can stem from multiple factors, including market volatility, operational inefficiencies, regulatory changes, and competitive pressures.

Firm Performance

Firm performance is defined as a corporation's actual outcomes compared to its expected goals and objectives, reflecting its overall efficiency, profitability, and strategic success. Richard et al., (2009) express three kinds of business consequences: (a) monetary performance (profits; return on assets; return on investment and so on); (b) merchandise marketplace performance (sales; market share and so on); and (c) stakeholder return (total stakeholder return, economic value added, etc.). The phrase "organizational effectiveness" encompasses a larger range of concepts.

Literature Review

The conflict of interest between owners and managers has intensified research focus on corporate governance (CG). Various theories have emerged to explain CG systems, offering diverse perspectives and strategies to mitigate agency issues while enhancing firm valuation. The following concepts provide a comprehensive understanding of corporate governance, forming the theoretical foundation for this research.

Sinnakkannu and Nassir (2008) revealed that shortcomings in corporate governance (CG) practices within organizations have been attributed to various fundamental factors. Without a robust CG framework, defining the roles and responsibilities of managers, directors, and stakeholders becomes challenging. The rise in corporate scandals, financial crises, and regulatory failures has driven investors and shareholders to demand greater transparency and protection of their wealth in organizational management (Gupta and Sharma, 2014). The shortcomings in corporate governance (CG) practices within organizations have been attributed to various fundamental factors. Without a robust CG framework, defining the roles and responsibilities of managers, directors, and stakeholders becomes challenging. The rise in corporate scandals, financial crises, and regulatory failures has driven investors and shareholders to demand greater transparency and protection of their wealth in organizational management.

Non-financial firms in Pakistan with institutional and foreign investors tend to outperform others. Companies with concentrated ownership experience fewer agency problems and demonstrate better overall performance (Ali et al., 2021). Corporate governance committees positively influence sustainability strengths and help mitigate risks. However, a higher sustainability score does not necessarily reduce risk concerns (Mehreen, 2021). Board size is positively associated with firm performance in Saudi Arabia, as reflected in both return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) models (Bazhair, 2021). These institutions typically include corporate laws, securities regulations, stock market listing requirements, established business practices, and prevailing ethical standards. Consequently, variations in Pakistan's corporate governance system are likely to have substantial effects on the structure and conduct of businesses within the country.

Pakistan's Corporate Governance

In Pakistan, corporate governance (CG) is a relatively recent phenomenon. The requirements of the Corporate Governance Code were incorporated into the listing regulations of all stock exchanges following its implementation by the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) in March 2002, in collaboration with the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Pakistan (ICAP). Key studies that have shaped these practices include the Cadbury Committee Report on the Financial Aspects of UK Corporate Governance (Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M., 2021) the Hampel Committee Report on Corporate Governance in the UK (Ow-yong & Guan, 2000, Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M., 2021), the King Committee Report on Corporate Governance in South Africa (2002), and the OECD Principles of Corporate Governance (1999).

The primary objective of the Corporate Governance Code is to establish a framework where corporations are directed and managed by executives in accordance with best practices to safeguard the interests of diverse stakeholders. It suggests reorganizing the composition of the board of directors to encourage broader participation from shareholders, as well as

polymaking and non-executive directors. It is often challenging for outsiders to understand a company's ownership structure, especially in the case of business conglomerates (Afza & Nazir, 2012; Younas et al., 2021). Therefore, changes in Pakistan's corporate governance system are expected to have significant implications for the structure and behavior of the country's corporations (Bebchuk & Cohen, 2005). There is growing interest in analyzing the impact of corporate governance on the Pakistani stock market, although many questions remain unresolved. This study aims to contribute to the existing literature on corporate governance in this context.

Firm Performance and Corporate Governance

The impact of corporate governance extends beyond supervisory functions designed for protection; it also influences corporate values. Previous studies have established a connection between corporate governance, organizational performance, and firm value (Bebchuk & Cohen, 2005; Brown & Caylor, 2004; Kyere & Ausloos, 2021). The study indicates a positive association between management team attributes and the organization's overall performance. On the other hand, there is no consensus on how to align corporate governance with the framework most strongly associated with equity and performance. Therefore, identifying effective co-management measures is essential. The first hypothesis to be tested to determine the validity of this theoretical expectation is:

H1: Corporate Governance contributes to higher firm performance.

H2: Corporate Governance contributes to lower firm risk.

Previous studies have examined the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance using rigorous ratings, with Tobin's Q serving as a proxy. Previous studies have examined the relationship between corporate governance and firm performance using rigorous ratings, with Tobin's Q serving as a proxy.

Independent Board of Directors

The directors on the board committee play a crucial role in overseeing the firm's management. As a result of these conflicts of interest, agency costs are incurred by the firm due to the need to manage agents, including monitoring and auditing expenses, as well as potential long-term damages (Dat et al., 2020). Since these costs are ultimately borne by the principals (shareholders), reducing agency costs becomes an essential part of the responsibility to maximize shareholder value. When managers (agents) have limited ownership, they may engage in actions that do not enhance shareholder value, particularly when they misuse the board's authority and oversight (Liu & Fong, 2010). An independent board is widely viewed as an effective governance structure, as it enhances the board's capacity to monitor management and align their actions with shareholder interests (Liu & Fong, 2010). External executives have incentives to protect their reputation, which motivates them to make decisions that are in the best interest of the company (Dat et al., 2020). Other key factors highlighted by Solomon (2010) for effective board formation include regular meetings, effective communication among board members and shareholders, a willingness to discuss proposals collaboratively at a high level of respect, attention to financial risk concerns, awareness, problem-solving, and any initiatives aimed at enhancing the company's efficiency.

Managerial Ownership (OH):

Salami, K. A. (2011) examined how ownership structure and the conflict of interest between shareholders within a poorly managed system affected a company's profitability. The literature reveals two opposing views on the relationship between management ownership and performance. One perspective suggests that management ownership may reduce performance, as manager-shareholders may engage in moral hazard behavior, leading to issues such as information asymmetry and agency conflicts. On the other hand, another perspective suggests that managerial ownership has a positive impact on performance due to the alignment of incentives between management and shareholders.

Board Ownership (BOH):

Several studies on corporate governance (CG) highlight the direct relationship between ownership structure and company performance. However, the findings of most previous research has indicated a positive link between institutional ownership and performance (Jiang & Kim, 2020). These mixed results suggest that the relationship between ownership structure and firm performance is complex and may depend on various contextual factors. As a result, the current study seeks to expand intellectual exploration of the relationship between corporate governance frameworks and firm performance. It aims to examine whether corporate board characteristics, such as board size and board independence, influence the relationship between ownership structure and firm resilience.

Institutional Investors (IH)

Institutional investors, including joint ventures and annuity funds, serve as influential and active regulators in Western economies (Jiang & Kim, 2020). Similar to major shareholders, banks make significant investments in firms and seek to maximize their returns. Additionally, banks serve as key financial providers, playing a crucial role in corporate financing (Jiang, & Kim, 2020; Kyere & Ausloos, 2021). Corporate governance (CG) refers to the mechanisms and processes through which companies are controlled and directed, ensuring the equitable distribution of rights and responsibilities among directors, shareholders, auditors, regulators, and other key stakeholders. It establishes the rules and principles guiding corporate actions, providing a structured framework for firms to achieve their strategic and financial objectives.

2.3.6 CEO Duality (CEOD)

The CEO's identity refers to the leadership structure within the board of directors, specifically whether the chief executive officer (CEO) and the equity holders are the same individual. Conversely, the management perspective argues against this separation, emphasizing the importance of leadership unity in corporate governance. The roles of equity holders and CEOs in corporate governance are

crucial, with a strong emphasis on maintaining board independence through the separation of these roles. Merging the CEO and board chairman positions can lead to heightened agency issues, weakened board authority, and conflicts of interest, ultimately undermining corporate governance and firm performance. To ensure impartial decision-making and effective oversight, it is recommended to keep these roles distinct, supported by clear accountability mechanisms and governance standards.

Firm Risk and Corporate Governance

Numerous studies have examined the relationship between corporate governance (CG) and firm performance (Salem et al., 2019). Strong CG practices positively impact business performance (Younas et al., 2021; Brown & Caylor, 2006). Companies with strong CG enable management to minimize risk exposure, such as by rejecting high-risk projects, leading to lower capital costs (Rehman et al., 2021). Numerous studies suggest that the board of directors plays a crucial role in influencing an organization's financial performance. Drobetz (2015) found that board committees positively impact financial outcomes, whereas Salem et al. (2019) reported the opposite. Additionally, the role of independent commissioners has been highlighted (Akbar, Hussain, Ahmad, & Hassan, 2020).

In contrast, Wang et al. (2019) observed that a higher percentage of ownership by blockholders and institutional investors is not strongly linked to increased risk. Instead, they suggest that blockholders and influential investors are more focused on monitoring and oversight rather than actively driving company profits.

H1: Corporate Governance practices positively contributes to firm performance during crises.

H2: Corporate Governance practices negatively contributes to firm risk during crises.

Methodology

This study incorporates several internal corporate governance (CG) elements into the model. Managerial ownership (MH) may lead to diverging perspectives on governance and operational decision-making. The managerial

shareholding influences their behavior, as managers who are not primary residual claimants are less likely to take excessive risks. However, managers with larger shareholdings are more wealth-sensitive and may avoid risk to protect their financial interests (Kim & Lu, 2011).

Conversely, Kini and Williams (2012) found that firms offer incentives that encourage directors to embrace risk-taking to enhance performance. In summary, managerial ownership plays a critical role in shaping a firm's risk exposure and overall performance.

Table 1. Variables, Abbreviations and Formula

Variable	Abbreviation	Formula
Return on Asset	ROA	Net Income
Firm size	Size	Ln (outstanding shares × share price)
Return on Equity	ROE	Net income / shareholders' equity
Assets	Ln Assets	Ln (total assets)
Age	Ln Age	Ln (age of the company)
Capital Expenditure	Cap Exp	(ΔPP&E + Current Depreciation)
CAPM Beta	Beta	(Stock return – risk free rate) / (market return – risk free rate)
Debt on equity	LEV	(Total liability / shareholders' equity)
Institutional ownership	INS	(Number of institutional shares / number of shares outstandings) x 100
CEO duality	CEO duality	Person holding the place of company CEO and chairman of the BOD (used as a dummy variable)
Independent directors of Board	IND	Amount of self-governing directors that that must comprise the board
Blockholder ownership	BH	Large block of busniess's shares and/or bonds
Managerial ownership	MH	(Number of managerial shares / number of shares outstaning) x 100
Board ownership	BOH	%age of shares occupied by the BOD
Earning per share	EPS	(total income – prefered sahre) / weighted average of common share outstandings
Tobin's Q	Tobin's Q	(market capitalization / total assets) x 100

Note: Where PP&E= Plant, property and equipment

Executives and superintendents serve as key governance proxies within an organization, as they possess in-depth knowledge of its operations and future prospects. While the board of directors is accountable to stakeholders, executives act as internal monitors, ensuring the protection of shareholder investments (Minnick & Noga, 2010). On the other hand, when corporate executives and superintendents are owned by a large number of shareholders and adequate checks and balances are lacking, the efficiency of the firm's internal governance declines (Fernández & Arrondo, 2005).

The third internal governance component is chief executive duality (CEOD), which refers to the scenario where the CEO and board chairman are the same individual. Conversely, Adams et al. (2005) argue that a powerful CEO has greater influence over business outcomes,

leading to higher stock volatility when the CEO and equity holders are the same person. Our model incorporates six key governance variables, reflecting dual dimensions of corporate governance: 1. Blockholder ownership, 2. Board independence, 3. Managerial ownership, 4. Board ownership, 5. Institutional stockholders, and 6. CEO duality (CEOD). The model framework is presented in Equation (1), summarizing the preceding analysis.

$$Performance_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 + \beta_2 (BOH)_{it} + \beta_3 (IH)_{it} + \beta_4 (IH)_{it} + \beta_5 (MH)_{it} + \beta_6 (CEOD)_{it} + \beta_7 \ln (Assets)_{it} + \beta_8 (Age)_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

This study explores the relationship between corporate governance (CG) and firm performance, utilizing three key performance

metrics: Tobin's Q, Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings Per Share (EPS). Additionally, it examines whether CG mechanisms can mitigate firm risk, measured by Value at Risk (VaR) at a 99% confidence level, which estimates potential financial losses over a given period. The study investigates whether strong CG practices effectively reduce firm risk, using VaR as the primary risk measure. The model quantifies the impact of CG mechanisms on both firm performance and risk exposure. This research provides valuable insights into the role of ownership structures, board composition, and governance practices in shaping corporate performance and risk management, highlighting the importance of effective CG in enhancing corporate stability and outcomes.

$$Risk_{it} = \beta_0 + \alpha_1(Risk)_{i,t-1} + \beta_1(BH)_{i,t-1} + \beta_2(MH)_{i,t-1} + \beta_3(BOH)_{i,t-1} + \beta_4(IH)_{i,t-1} + \beta_5(IND)_{i,t-1} + \beta_6(CEOD)_{i,t-1} + \beta_7(LEV)_{i,t} + \beta_8 \ln(Age)_{it} + \beta_9(CapEx)_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$VaR_{x,t} = \bar{r}_{x,y} \pm t_{0,99} \delta_{x,t} \quad (3)$$

Risk represents business risk, measured by xt VaR and xt VaR 5, which are estimated using firm x's daily returns for a given year t. The concept of Value at Risk (VaR) as a risk assessment tool was originally introduced by J.P. Morgan, providing a quantitative measure of potential financial losses over a specific time horizon at a given confidence level. To assess market risk, several international financial organizations have adopted internal models based on the Value at Risk (VaR) methodology.

Control Variables: Ln LEV: Natural logarithm of the leverage ratio (LEV), representing the debt ratio. CapEX: Capital expenditures, indicating a firm's investment in fixed assets. Ln

AGE: Natural logarithm of firm age, measured in centuries of operation. Additionally, corporate governance crises are represented by a dummy variable (DCG), capturing the impact of governance failures on firm risk and performance.

$$Performance_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1(BH * DCG)_{it} + \beta_2(MH * DCG)_{it} + \beta_3(BOH * DCG)_{it} + \beta_4(IH * DCG)_{it} + \beta_5(IND * DCG)_{it} + \beta_6(CEOD * DCG)_{it} + \beta_7 \ln(Assets * DCG)_{it} + \beta_8(Age * DCG)_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

$$Risk_{it} = \beta_0 + \alpha_1(Risk * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_1(BH * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_2(MH * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_3(BOH * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_4(IH * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_5(IND * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_6(CEOD * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \beta_7(LEV * DCG)_{i,t} + \beta_8 \ln(Age * DCG)_{it} + \beta_9(CapEx * DCG)_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

Results and Analysis

This study employed a range of data diagnostic tests to validate retrospective assumptions, using EViews 9. Skewness and kurtosis values were used to assess data normality, while the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance values were analyzed to detect multicollinearity among independent variables. Additionally, the Hausman test was used to determine whether a random effects model or a fixed effects model was more appropriate, considering serial correlation and heteroscedasticity within the dataset.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics provide a structured framework and encompass various strategies for summarizing, organizing, and analyzing data, allowing for a clearer understanding of patterns and trends within a dataset.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
Variable	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	SD. Error
ROE	781	-57.01	315.000	18.414	24.354	4.612	0.087
EPS	779	-50.510	261.230	8.059	19.777	5.160	0.088
TQS	780	1.00	1.670	1.266	0.183	0.514	0.088
Risk	781	-1.00	1.000	0.022	0.158	4.722	0.087
BH	781	0.00	4.000	1.690	1.252	0.470	0.087
BOH	781	0.000	86.791	31.785	22.902	0.142	0.087
IH	781	0.000	7.000	1.422	1.719	1.788	0.087
IND	781	0.000	5.000	2.323	1.687	0.315	0.087
MH	781	0.000	7.000	1.424	1.782	1.789	0.087
CEOD	781	0.000	1.000	0.575	0.499	-.303	0.087
LnAssets	781	0.000	11.984	9.954	1.285	-2.454	0.087
LnAge	781	0.000	4.726	3.534	0.666	-.998	0.087
LnLev	781	0.000	2.762	0.568	0.552	1.247	0.087
LnCE	780	0.000	21.001	14.365	4.188	-2.628	0.088

When the higher values are negative, the calculations use the highest ROE and EPS, indicating that the mean is more representative than the lowest values, as both the mean and higher figures fall on the same side. Tobin's Q (TQS) aligns with these metrics, with all top values positioned similarly. The risk measure has a mean of 0.022, with a range from -1 to 1, suggesting that the magnitude of risk is relatively low compared to the highest and lowest values. The standard deviations (SD) of ROE (24.354) and EPS (19.777) indicate a greater deviation from the mean, reflecting higher variability. Similarly, BOH (Board Ownership) has an SD of 22.902, showing significant dispersion from the

mean. While some proxies exhibit a narrower spread, Ray's (2012) study suggests that the acceptable range for skewness should fall between -5 and +5. As a result, the scaling of all variables is justified and remains widely applicable.

Multicollinearity Statistics

When independent variables in a study exhibit a high degree of similarity, it is referred to as multicollinearity. If the correlation among variables is significantly high, it can potentially compromise the model's reliability, affecting the accuracy of coefficient estimates and leading to reduced explanatory power.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Statistics

Variable	Multicollinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
ROE	0.093	1.107
EPS	0.924	1.083
TQS	0.966	1.036
Risk	0.98	1.02
BH	0.959	1.042
BOH	0.854	1.171
IND	0.956	1.046
MH	0.905	1.105
CEOD	0.84	1.19
LnAssets	0.826	1.21
LnAge	0.14	7.121
LnLev	0.965	1.037
LnCE	0.935	1.07

Hausman Test

The Hausman test was utilized to determine whether a random effects model or a fixed effects model is more appropriate for the analysis. The test hypotheses are as follows:

H_0 (Null Hypothesis): The random effects model is appropriate.

H_1 (Alternative Hypothesis): The fixed effects model is appropriate.

If the p-value of the Hausman test is significant (typically < 0.05), the fixed effects model is preferred. Otherwise, the random effects model is deemed suitable.

Table 4. Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects			
Hausman Test			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random ROE	3.717096	5	0.5908
Cross-section random EPS	10.013376	5	0.0749
Cross-section random TQS	4.925505	5	0.425

The null hypothesis ($p > 0.05$) is accepted for all dependent variables in Table 4.4 (ROE, EPS, and TQS). As a result, despite the nature of the dependent variables (proxies) in the first model, the random effects model is deemed more appropriate and is therefore recommended for analyzing ROE, EPS, and TQS.

Random Model Effect

A random effects model is a statistical model that estimates and analyzes parameters that vary over time rather than remaining fixed. In this model, each data mean represents a combination of random variations, meaning that the mean is not constant across all data sets. Instead, it accounts for unobserved heterogeneity, assuming that individual differences are random and uncorrelated with the explanatory variables.

ROE (Dependent Variable)

Table 5. ROE (DV)

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random-effects)				
Variable	Co-efficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	47.38523	12.69188	3.733507	0.0002
BH	-2.6658	1.667593	-1.598591	0.1103
BOH	0.069311	0.055349	1.252245	0.2109
IH	-3.032124	6.511833	-0.465633	0.6416
MH	5.236557	6.608941	0.792344	0.4284
IND	1.463165	1.249682	1.17083	0.242
CEOD	-3.785254	4.11846	-0.919095	0.3583
LNASSETS	-0.33957	0.788062	-0.430893	0.6667
LNAGE	-7.824655	2.383119	-3.283367	0.0011
R-squared	0.025723	Mean dependent var		5.563201
Adjusted R-squared	0.015627	S.D. dependent var		17.63558

S.E. of regression	17.49724	Sum squared resid	236350.5
F-statistic	2.547834	Durbin-Watson stat	0.633007
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009619		

EPS (Dependent Variable)

Table 6. EPS (DV)

Method: Panel EGLS-(Cross-section random-effects)				
Variable	Co-efficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.630232	9.37283	0.06724	0.9464
BH	-1.613836	0.914502	-1.764716	0.078
BOH	0.099728	0.043033	2.317503	0.0207
IH	-0.007014	6.441137	-0.001089	0.9991
MH	1.308711	6.462908	0.202496	0.8396
IND	0.899294	0.685619	1.311652	0.19
CEOD	4.495425	2.371867	1.895311	0.0584
LNASSETS	0.635912	0.694652	0.91544	0.3602
LNAGE	-1.663484	1.615851	-1.029479	0.3036
R-squared	0.023756	Mean dependent var		4.471234
Adjusted R-squared	0.013613	S.D. dependent var		17.76145
S.E. of regression	17.64063	Sum squared resid		239617.7
F-statistic	2.342151	Durbin-Watson stat		2.174715
Prob(F-statistic)	0.017245			

TQS(Dependent Variable)

Table 7. TQS (DV)

Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section random effects)				
Variable	Co-efficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob .
C	1.039164	0.087378	11.89278	0.0000
BH	0.011133	0.00835	1.333391	0.1828
BOH	0.000104	0.000401	0.259546	0.7953
IH	-0.055761	0.061689	-0.903901	0.3663
MH	0.062678	0.06187	1.013068	0.3113
IND	0.001898	0.006254	0.303482	0.7616
CEOD	-0.002491	0.021709	-0.11473	0.9087
LNASSETS	0.010066	0.006546	1.537711	0.1245
LNAGE	0.024563	0.014916	1.646763	0.1
R-squared	0.012699	Mean dependent var		0.735502
Adjusted R-squared	0.002454	S.D. dependent var		0.168879
S.E. of regression	0.168714	Sum squared resid		21.94606
F-statistic	1.239561	Durbin-Watson stat		1.202748
Prob(F-statistic)	0.272723			

The issue of sequence problems arises when data points are connected in an inconsistent manner. The Durbin-Watson test typically yields values between 1.5 and 2.5, which do not necessarily indicate the absence of autocorrelation. In this study, the Hausman test was employed to determine the appropriate model between fixed and random effects, addressing the issue of sequential correlation. The Durbin-Watson values obtained for the performance proxies Return on Equity (ROE), Earnings per Share (EPS), and Tobin's Q Score (TQS) were 0.63, 2.1, and 1.2, respectively. To mitigate the challenge of serial correlation, a random-effects model was adopted. The F-statistic results indicate that the linear regression model provides a significantly better fit compared to a model without independent variables. Additionally, the F-statistic yielded a probability value of 0.000000 ($P < 0.05$), confirming the overall robustness and validity of the model.

Furthermore, the R-squared values demonstrate the extent to which variability in the dependent variables is explained by the predictors and control variables. After specifying the random-

effects model and incorporating cross-sectional fixed effects, the average R-squared values across the sub-models for ROE, EPS, and TQS were 0.53, 0.28, and 0.23, respectively.

The analysis of corporate governance proxies, as presented in Table 4.4, indicates no significant relationship between these proxies and ROE, suggesting a lack of association with firm ownership. However, the control variable LNAGE exhibits a strong inverse relationship with share returns. In contrast, Table 4.6 reveals that, with the exception of Board Ownership (BOH), all proxies for co-management equity are significantly associated with EPS. The insignificance of executive compensation per share appears to be linked to managerial flexibility. Notably, apart from board ownership, none of the corporate governance proxies contributed to firm value acquisition. Moreover, Table 4.6 suggests that while all corporate governance proxies and control variables are significantly associated with TQS, they do not exhibit a meaningful link to stable market value.

Second Model

Table 8. Risk (DV)

Method: Panel Least Squares				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.00396	0.056395	-0.070211	0.944
RISK1	0.327621	0.034123	9.601265	0
BH	0.001666	0.004354	0.382724	0.702
BOH	3.48E-05	0.000248	0.140267	0.8885
IH	0.004417	0.053304	0.082872	0.934
MH	-0.004536	0.053313	-0.085081	0.9322
IND	0.002791	0.003257	0.856845	0.3918
CEOD	-0.010679	0.0116	-0.920602	0.3575
LNASSETS	8.14E-05	0.004572	0.017807	0.9858
LNAGE	0.009687	0.0084	1.153184	0.2492
LNCE	-0.001539	0.001333	-1.15508	0.2484
LNLEV	0.003001	0.00992	0.302544	0.7623
R-squared	0.118847	Mean dependent var		0.021917
Adjusted R-squared	0.10621	S.D. dependent var		0.158975
S.E. of regression	0.150296	Akaike info criterion		-0.937136
Sum squared resid	17.32567	Schwarz criterion		-0.865383
Log likelihood	377.0146	Hannan-Quinn criter .		-0.909537
F-statistic	9.404608	Durbin-Watson stat		2.170483
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

Similarly, in this case, the Durbin-Watson statistic is 2.17, indicating no significant autocorrelation. The F-statistic is significant at Prob (F-Statistics: 0.000000, $P < 0.05$), confirming the model's robustness and goodness of fit. Additionally, the R-squared value for the second model, where Risk is the dependent variable, falls within the acceptable range.

The analysis reveals that all previously measured corporate governance (CG) proxies and control variables exhibit no significant relationship with market risk, suggesting that corporate governance factors do not influence the firm's current market risk. However, the prior year's risk factor, denoted as Risk1, demonstrates a strong and statistically significant relationship with the dependent variable (Risk), as indicated by its t-statistic of 9 and a probability value of $P < 0.05$. This finding suggests that Risk1 has a direct and positive effect on Risk, implying that an elevated risk level in the previous year leads to an increased risk level in the current year. The study finds that CG is not a significant determinant of market risk.

Discussion

The analysis indicates that corporate governance (CG) mechanisms exhibit no significant relationship with shareholder returns, suggesting they do not enhance stockholder value. Similarly, CG mechanisms show no substantial association with earnings per share (EPS), except for board ownership (BOH), which demonstrates a notable correlation. Among the control variables, LNAGE is negatively associated with shareholder returns but remains insignificant for EPS. Additionally, neither CG mechanisms nor control variables display a meaningful relationship with Tobin's Q, implying no significant influence on the company's market valuation. Overall, with the exception of BOH, CG mechanisms fail to contribute meaningfully to shareholder returns, EPS, or market value.

The Risk1 factor is, therefore, highly significant and underscores the severity of market risk. Moving forward, current market risk factors are directly influenced by strong prior market risk factors. If the present market risk level is high, it

is likely that future market risk will also be elevated. The Risk1 factor is, therefore, highly significant and underscores the severity of market risk. Moving forward, current market risk factors are directly influenced by strong prior market risk factors. If the present market risk level is high, it is likely that future market risk will also be elevated.

Conclusion

In the initial model, all CG proxies exhibit an insignificant relationship with shareholder returns, suggesting no association between corporate governance and shareholder returns. However, LNAGE is found to be significantly and negatively associated with shareholder returns. This implies that, in this context, CG proxies do not contribute to shareholder returns. Similarly, all CG proxies, except for BOH, are insignificantly linked to EPS, while control variables also show no significant association with EPS. Thus, board ownership (BOH) is the only CG proxy that has a notable impact on EPS. Furthermore, neither CG proxies nor control variables exhibit a significant relationship with Tobin's Q, indicating no effect on the firm's market value. Consequently, corporate governance mechanisms, apart from BOH, do not contribute to enhancing shareholder returns, EPS, or market valuation.

In the second model, all CG proxies and control variables remain insignificantly associated with risk, suggesting no connection between corporate governance and the firm's current market risk. However, the previous year's risk factor (Risk1) demonstrates a significant and positive relationship with the dependent variable (Risk). This finding indicates that prior market risk levels have a direct influence on current market risk within the financial sector. If the risk level in the preceding year was high, it is likely that the current year's risk level will also be elevated.

The study concludes that, among CG proxies, only board ownership (BOH) has a significant impact on the firm's performance, particularly on earnings per share, whereas all other proxies remain insignificant. Strengthening corporate

governance mechanisms may enhance firm performance and contribute to the overall financial development of the industry. Additionally, Risk1 is identified as the only significant predictor of risk volatility, while CG and control variables have a negligible influence on risk indicators. Following the global financial crisis, many firms experienced governance and management failures due to inadequate risk control, leading to poor performance. Effective governance and risk management practices may mitigate past risk levels, thereby improving present and future performance.

References

- Adams, R. B., & Mehran, H. (2005, August). Corporate performance, board structure and its determinants in the banking industry. In EFA 2005 Moscow Meetings. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.302593>
- Afza, T., & Nazir, M. S. (2012). Role of corporate governance in operating performance enhancement of mergers and acquisitions in Pakistan. *Elixir Finance*, 42, 6447–6456.
- Akbar, M., Hussain, S., Ahmad, T., & Hassan, S. (2020). Corporate governance and firm performance in Pakistan: Dynamic panel estimation.
- Ali, S., Fei, G., Ali, Z., & Hussain, F. (2021). Corporate governance and firm performance: Evidence from listed firms of Pakistan. *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability RISUS*, 12(1), 170–187. <https://doi.org/10.23925/2179-3565.2021v12i1p170-187>
- Bazhair, A. H. (2021). Corporate governance mechanism and firm performance in Saudi Arabia. *Studies of Applied Economics*, 39(4). <https://doi.org/10.25115/eea.v39i4.4317>
- Bebchuk, L. A., & Cohen, A. (2005). The costs of entrenched boards. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 78(2), 409–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2004.09.002>
- Black, B. S., De Carvalho, A. G., Khanna, V. S., Kim, W., & Yurtoglu, B. B. (2020). Which aspects of corporate governance do and do not matter in emerging markets. *Journal of Law, Finance, and Accounting*, 5(1), 137–177. <https://doi.org/10.1561/108.00000043>
- Brown, L. D., & Caylor, M. L. (2006). Corporate governance and firm valuation. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 25(4), 409–434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaccpubpol.2006.05.005>
- Ciftci, I., Tatoglu, E., Wood, G., Demirbag, M., & Zaim, S. (2019). Corporate governance and firm performance in emerging markets: Evidence from Turkey. *International Business Review*, 28(1), 90–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2018.08.004>
- Dat, P. M., Mau, N. D., Loan, B. T. T., & Huy, D. T. N. (2020). Comparative China corporate governance standards after financial crisis, corporate scandals and manipulation. *Journal of Security & Sustainability Issues*, 9(3). [https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.9.3\(18\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jssi.2020.9.3(18))
- Fernández, C., & Arrondo, R. (2005). Alternative internal controls as substitutes of the board of directors. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 13(6), 856–866. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2005.00476.x>
- Gupta, P., & Sharma, A. M. (2014). A study of the impact of corporate governance practices on firm performance in Indian and South Korean companies. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133, 4–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.163>
- Jiang, F., & Kim, K. A. (2020). Corporate governance in China: A survey. *Review of Finance*, 24(4), 733–772. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rof/rfz045>
- Kim, E. H., & Lu, Y. (2011). CEO ownership, external governance, and risk-taking. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 102(2), 272–292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2011.07.002>
- Kini, O., & Williams, R. (2012). Tournament incentives, firm risk, and corporate policies.

Journal of Financial Economics, 103(2), 350–376.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2011.09.007>

Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M. (2021). Corporate governance and firms' financial performance in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), 1871–1885.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.1883>

Lau, C., Lu, Y., & Liang, Q. (2016). Corporate social responsibility in China: A corporate governance approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 136(1), 73–87.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2513-0>

Liu, H., & Fong, M. W. L. (2010). Board characteristics of medium and large Chinese companies. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 10(2), 163–175.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/14720701011035684>

Mehreen, R. (2021). Does corporate sustainability and corporate governance pay off for firm's risk? *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(11), 534.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14110534>

Minnick, K., & Noga, T. (2010). Do corporate governance characteristics influence tax management? *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 16(5), 703–718.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2010.08.005>

Rehman, H., Ramzan, M., Haq, M. Z. U., Hwang, J., & Kim, K. B. (2021). Risk management in corporate governance framework. *Sustainability*, 13(9), 5015.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095015>

Richard, P. J., Devinney, T. M., Yip, G. S., & Johnson, G. (2009). Measuring organizational performance: Towards methodological best practice. *Journal of Management*, 35(3), 718–804.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206308330560>

Salami, K. A. (2011). Analysis of the relationship between share ownership structure, corporate governance structure, and corporate investment efficiency, using GSE market data (2005–2009). *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 11(4), 111–118.

Salem, I. H., Ayadi, S. D., & Hussainey, K. (2019). Corporate governance and risk disclosure quality: Tunisian evidence. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 9(4), 567–602.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-01-2019-0005>

Sinnakkannu, J., & Nassir, A. M. (2008). Revisiting the causes of the East Asian financial crisis: Was it predictable? *Journal of Economic & Management Perspectives*, 2(2), 78–90.

Solomon, J. (2020). *Corporate governance and accountability* (5th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.

Wang, J. Y., Wang, J. L., & Liao, H. Y. (2019). Does corporate governance enhance firm performance and reduce firm risk? Evidence from Taiwanese listed companies. *Journal of Economics*, 15(1), 61–91.

Younas, N., UdDin, S., Awan, T., & Khan, M. Y. (2021). Corporate governance and financial distress: Asian emerging market perspective. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(5), 909–930.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-10-2020-0446>